

Effect of temperature and solvents on speed of ultrasound and allied acoustical parameters of epoxy ricinol of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)anthrone-10 solutions

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Abstract : Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of ultrasound (U) (2 MHz) of pure solvents (chloroform, THF and 1,4-dioxane) and solutions of epoxy ricinol of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)anthrone-10 (EANRA) solutions have been investigated at 303, 308 and 313 K. Specific acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), intermolecular free path length (L_f), classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$) and viscous relaxation time (τ) have been determined from ρ , η and U data and are correlated with concentration. Z , $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ and τ increased with C and decreased with T , while κ_s and L_f decreased with C and increased with T in the solvent systems studied. A fairly good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration is observed at 303, 308 and 313 K and solvent systems studied. Linear increase or decrease of acoustical parameters with concentration and temperature indicated existence of strong molecular interactions. EANRA has structure forming tendency.

Keywords : Speed of ultrasound, acoustical parameters, density, viscosity, molecular interactions.

Introduction

Ultrasonic technique is extensively useful in polymer processing technology. It is useful to understand the structures of polymers¹⁻³ and also in investigation of organic liquids, liquid mixtures, electrolyte solutions, microstructure and mechanical properties of metals^{4,5}. It also finds its applications in medicine, biology, process industries, etc.¹. Ultrasonic measurements provide information about strength and nature of molecular interactions in the solutions and behavior of polymer chains in an ultrasonic field⁶.

Castor oil is a triglyceride and contains ~90% rici-

noleic acid, 6-2% oleic acid and 5-1% linoleic acid as fatty acid chains, which are useful in the synthesis of polyester polyols [Mw 500-5000] for various purposes. Due to good flexibility and chemical resistance of polyesters, they are most widely used in wood and plastic coating, antigrffiti and aircraft coatings.

To our knowledge no work has been reported on ultrasonic studies of epoxy ricinol of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)anthrone-10, here after designated as EANRA (I), which encouraged us to investigate the effect of concentration, temperature and nature of solvents on molecular interactions in EANRA solutions.

(I) EANRA

Experimental

Materials :

Chloroform (CF), tetrahydrofuran (THF) and 1,4-dioxane (DO) used in the present study were of laboratory grade and purified according to literature methods⁷. EANRA (acid value 6.62 mg KOH/g, hydroxyl value 935.2 mg KOH/g and weight average molecular weight 5300) was synthesized and purified three times from chloroform-*n*-hexane system prior to its use. The 2% solutions of EANRA were prepared in selected solvents and from them a series of dilute solutions were prepared at room temperature.

The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of ultrasound (U) of pure solvents and EANRA solutions were carried out at 303, 308 and 313 \pm 0.1 K by using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi), Model No. F-81, operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U measurements were accurate to ± 0.1 kg/m³, 0.01 mPas and $\pm 0.15\%$, respectively.

Theoretical equations for acoustical parameters;

Specific acoustical impedance :

$$Z = U \rho \tag{1}$$

Isentropic compressibility :

$$\kappa_s = \frac{1}{U^2 \rho} \tag{2}$$

Intermolecular free path length :

$$L_f = K (\kappa_s)^{1/2} \tag{3}$$

where $K = (93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8}$ is a temperature dependent constant.

Classical absorption coefficient :

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2} \right)_{cl} = \frac{8\pi^2 \eta}{3U^3 \rho} \tag{4}$$

Classical absorption coefficient has its origin in the viscosity of the medium.

Viscous relaxation time :

The resistance offered by viscous force in the flow of sound wave appears as a classical absorption associated

with viscous relaxation time :

$$\tau = \frac{4\eta}{3\rho U^2} \tag{5}$$

Results and discussion

Experimental data on ρ , η and U of pure solvents and EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K are summarized in Table 1 and correlated with concentration (C) and temperature (T). The least square equations along with regression coefficients (R^2) are reported in Table 2 from

Fig. 1. The plots of Z against C for EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of ultrasound (U) data of EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K

Conc (%)	Density ρ (kg/m ³)			Viscosity $\eta \times 10^3$ (mPas)			U (m s ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
EANRA-CF									
0	1475.7	1472.9	1467.9	0.569	0.536	0.478	968.4	949.6	931.6
0.25	1476.9	1472.3	1467.4	0.584	0.543	0.489	966.8	949.6	933.2
0.50	1476.3	1471.7	1467.1	0.588	0.549	0.495	968	950.4	934.4
1	1475.4	1470.2	1466.4	0.604	0.567	0.508	970.4	954.4	936
1.50	1474.5	1469.3	1465.8	0.628	0.583	0.521	974	954.4	938.8
2.0	1473.5	1468.4	1465.4	0.656	0.604	0.538	974.8	956.8	941.2
EANRA-DO									
0	1027.5	1025.9	1022.1	1.131	1.043	0.892	1327.2	1307.6	1287.2
0.25	1028.0	1026.4	1022.9	1.156	1.063	0.909	1330.8	1308	1290.4
0.50	1028.8	1027.1	1024	1.173	1.084	0.926	1332	1308.8	1290.8
1	1029.4	1028.3	1025.7	1.208	1.111	0.957	1334	1310.8	1293.6
1.50	1030.0	1029.1	1026.2	1.246	1.143	0.987	1336	1316	1294
2.0	1031.7	1030.9	1027.6	1.296	1.181	1.028	1336	1318	1296.8
EANRA-THF									
0	883.3	881	878.6	0.490	0.454	0.397	1255.6	1229.6	1210
0.25	885.4	881.9	880.8	0.499	0.457	0.411	1256.4	1230	1213.6
0.50	886.5	882.8	882.6	0.510	0.469	0.419	1258.4	1231.6	1215.2
1	887.7	883.9	883.2	0.525	0.484	0.432	1259.6	1233.6	1216.8
1.50	889.2	885.5	884.9	0.551	0.505	0.449	1260.4	1236.8	1218.8
2.0	890.5	886.9	886.4	0.570	0.525	0.464	1262	1238.8	1220.8

Table 2. The least square equations and regression coefficients for EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K

Parameters	Least square equations (Regression coefficients, R^2) for		
	303 K	308 K	313 K
EANRA-CF			
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	$-1.904C + 1477$ ($R^2 = 0.998$)	$-2.253C + 1472$ ($R^2 = 0.987$)	$-1.173C + 1467$ ($R^2 = 0.990$)
η (mPas)	$0.041C + 0.568$ ($R^2 = 0.975$)	$0.035C + 0.532$ ($R^2 = 0.996$)	$0.027C + 0.481$ ($R^2 = 0.994$)
U (m s ⁻¹)	$4.878C + 965.6$ ($R^2 = 0.970$)	$4.322C + 948.8$ ($R^2 = 0.937$)	$4.546C + 931.9$ ($R^2 = 0.992$)
$Z, 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	$0.005C + 1.426$ ($R^2 = 0.945$)	$0.004C + 1.397$ ($R^2 = 0.899$)	$0.005C + 1.367$ ($R^2 = 0.987$)
$\kappa_s, 10^{-10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	$-0.063C + 7.258$ ($R^2 = 0.961$)	$-0.056C + 7.542$ ($R^2 = 0.922$)	$-0.069C + 7.844$ ($R^2 = 0.990$)
$L_1, 10^{-11}$ (m)	$-0.024C + 5.640$ ($R^2 = 0.961$)	$-0.021C + 5.750$ ($R^2 = 0.923$)	$-0.026C + 5.864$ ($R^2 = 0.990$)
$\tau, 10^{-13}$ (s)	$0.344C + 5.506$ ($R^2 = 0.970$)	$0.237C + 5.034$ ($R^2 = 0.994$)	$0.309C + 5.354$ ($R^2 = 0.992$)
$(\alpha/f^2)_{Cl}, 10^{-14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)	$0.065C + 1.126$ ($R^2 = 0.985$)	$0.058C + 1.113$ ($R^2 = 0.987$)	$0.044C + 1.065$ ($R^2 = 0.994$)

EANRA-DO			
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1.904C + 1027 (R ² = 0.952)	2.443C + 1025 (R ² = 0.984)	2.539C + 1022 (R ² = 0.964)
η (mPas)	0.079C + 1.132 (R ² = 0.993)	0.065C + 1.047 (R ² = 0.996)	0.066C + 0.891 (R ² = 0.996)
U (m s ⁻¹)	3.151C + 1330 (R ² = 0.927)	6.107C + 1305 (R ² = 0.965)	3.570C + 1289 (R ² = 0.956)
$Z, 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.005C + 1.367 (R ² = 0.989)	0.009C + 1.339 (R ² = 0.989)	0.006C + 1.318 (R ² = 0.970)
$\kappa_s, 10^{-10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-0.035C + 5.497 (R ² = 0.975)	-0.065C + 5.715 (R ² = 0.982)	-0.045C + 5.881 (R ² = 0.966)
$L_f, 10^{-11}$ (m)	-0.016C + 4.909 (R ² = 0.975)	-0.029C + 5.005 (R ² = 0.982)	-0.020C + 5.077 (R ² = 0.966)
$\tau, 10^{-13}$ (s)	0.516C + 8.304 (R ² = 0.989)	0.394C + 7.986 (R ² = 0.992)	0.457C + 6.995 (R ² = 0.995)
$(\alpha f^2)_{cl}, 10^{-14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)	0.073C + 1.231 (R ² = 0.985)	0.053C + 1.206 (R ² = 0.988)	0.066C + 1.069 (R ² = 0.996)
EANRA-THF			
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	2.846C + 884.8 (R ² = 0.995)	2.817C + 881.2 (R ² = 0.996)	2.953C + 880.4 (R ² = 0.965)
η (mPas)	0.040C + 0.488 (R ² = 0.994)	0.038C + 0.447 (R ² = 0.995)	0.03C + 0.403 (R ² = 0.997)
U (m s ⁻¹)	2.858C + 1256 (R ² = 0.941)	5.053C + 1228 (R ² = 0.994)	3.970C + 1212 (R ² = 0.994)
$Z, 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.006C + 1.111 (R ² = 0.980)	0.008C + 1.082 (R ² = 0.995)	0.007C + 1.067 (R ² = 0.983)
$\kappa_s, 10^{-10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-0.055C + 7.159 (R ² = 0.970)	-0.084C + 7.514 (R ² = 0.995)	-0.075C + 7.720 (R ² = 0.986)
$L_f, 10^{-11}$ (m)	-0.021C + 5.602 (R ² = 0.970)	-0.032C + 5.739 (R ² = 0.995)	-0.028C + 5.817 (R ² = 0.987)
$\tau, 10^{-13}$ (s)	0.342C + 4.667 (R ² = 0.992)	0.324C + 4.489 (R ² = 0.995)	0.261C + 4.155 (R ² = 0.997)
$(\alpha f^2)_{cl}, 10^{-14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)	0.517C + 7.327 (R ² = 0.990)	0.486C + 7.205 (R ² = 0.995)	0.400C + 6.756 (R ² = 0.997)

which it is observed that a good to excellent correlation is observed. From Table 1, it is clear that ρ decreased linearly with concentration (C) and temperature (T) in CF, while it increased linearly with C and decreased with T in DO and THF. The η and U both increased linearly with C and decreased with T in all the three systems. The observed trends in ρ , η and U are CF > DO > THF, DO > CF > THF and DO > THF > CF, respectively. The change in ρ and U with C and T are not as appreciable as η due to intermolecular motion by molecular interactions⁸⁻¹².

The linear increase of ρ , η and U with C confirmed

increase of cohesive forces because of strong molecular interactions, while decrease of these parameters with T supported decrease of cohesive forces. The increase in temperature has two opposite effects namely structure formation (intermolecular association) and structure destruction. The structure forming tendency is mainly due to solute-solvent interactions, while destruction of structure formed previously is due to thermal fluctuations. When thermal energy is greater than that of interaction energy, it causes destruction in structure formed previously.

In order to understand the effect of concentration, tem-

Fig. 2. The plots of κ_s against C for EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K.

perature, nature of solvents and solute on molecular interactions in solutions, various acoustical parameters such as specific acoustic impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), intermolecular free path length (L_f), classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$) and viscous relaxation time (τ) are determined according to above mentioned standard relations and are correlated with C and T (Figs. 1–5). The least square equations and regression coefficients are summarized in Table 2, from which a fairly good to excellent correlation between a particular parameter and

Fig. 3. The plots of L_f against C for EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K.

C is observed for a given temperature and solvent system studied.

The Z ($R^2 = 0.90-0.995$), τ ($R^2 = 0.970-0.997$) and $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ ($R^2 = 0.994-0.997$) increased linearly with C and decreased with T , while κ_s ($R^2 = 0.922-0.995$), and L_f ($R^2 = 0.923-0.995$) both decreased linearly with C and increased with T in CF, DO and THF. Increase or decrease of acoustical parameters with C and T indicated

Fig. 4. The plots of $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ against C for EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K.

presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. The ester, ether, carbonyl and hydroxyl groups of EANRA are polar groups, which are responsible for structure formation with solvents, i.e. molecular association. It is likely that OH groups of EANRA form H-bonds with Cl atoms of CF and lone pairs of electrons of THF and DO, while ester and carbonyl groups form H-bonds with H atom of

Fig. 5. The plots of τ against C for EANRA solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K.

CF. Due to modification of the structure of the solute both apparent molar volume as well as molecular weight will change and consequently ρ , η and U also change with C and T . Linear increase or decrease of the acoustical parameters with C confirmed predominant solvent-solute interactions over solute-solute interactions and dispersion forces.

Conclusions :

Strong molecular interactions exist in the solutions and EANRA has structure forming tendency in the solution state.

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